

SHERATON GRAND

Bengaluru Whitefield
Hotel & Convention Center

April 19th, 2022

TO WHOM IT MAY CONCERN

This is to certify that **Gaurav R** a student of **Srinivas University, Mangalore** has successfully completed his Industrial Training in **Culinary, Food & Beverage, Front Office, & Housekeeping** in our organization from 11th ~~December~~ 2021 to 18th April, 2022.

During his tenure we found him to be sincere, hardworking and diligent. We wish him success in all his future endeavours.

For Sheraton Grand Bengaluru Whitefield Hotel & Convention Centre

Shashi Prabha
Human Resources Associate
Sheraton Grand
Bengaluru-48
Grand Bengaluru Whitefield Hotel & Convention Center
A Unit of Sai Chakra Hotels Pvt. Ltd.

Sheraton Grand Bengaluru Whitefield Hotel & Convention Center

Prestige Shantiniketan Hoodi, Whitefield, Bengaluru - 560048

T +91 80 7100 8100 F +91 80 7100 8101

sheraton.com/bengaluruwhitefield

Sheraton Grand Bengaluru Whitefield Hotel & Convention Center (A Unit of Sai Chakra Hotels Pvt. Ltd.) GSTN: 29AAQCS7527K2ZG

April 19th, 2022

Letter of Appreciation

Dear Gaurav,

I would like to put on record the excellent contribution made by you during your On Job Training at our Hotel in F&B Service Department.

We appreciate your sincerity and dedication and would like to “Thank You” for your enthusiasm to learn and deliver as per our Brand and Hotel Expectation.

We wish you success in all your future endeavours.

For Sheraton Grand Bengaluru Whitefield Hotel & Convention Center

Shashi Prabha
Human Resources Associate

Sheraton Grand

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Prestige Shantiniketan,
Hoodi, Whitefield, Bengaluru,
Karnataka 560048 India
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F +91 80 7100 8101
sheraton.com/bengaluruwhitefield